

THE IMPLEMENTATION AND HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE IDEAS IN CHEMICAL ENTERPRISES IN THE 1970–1980S

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the processes of implementing innovative ideas in the chemical industry of Uzbekistan during the 1970–1980s, analyzing their economic efficiency and practical significance. Particular attention is paid to the introduction of scientific and technological progress into production, the growth in the levels of automation and mechanization, as well as the formation of new technologies and research directions. Alongside notable achievements, the study also objectively highlights existing challenges in the sector, including outdated equipment, insufficient levels of automation, and organizational shortcomings.

In 1970, under the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, the Republican Council for Assistance to Scientific and Technological Progress was established. Within this body, commissions and sections were created to study various problems; however, most of them remained largely formal in nature. A successful example of the implementation of scientific and technological progress can be observed at the Chirchik Electrochemical Plant. In 1966, a Department of Scientific Labor Organization was established at the enterprise. By 1971, the level of mechanization and automation of the main production processes and auxiliary operations reached 82.5%. As a result of the introduction of new machinery and technologies, as well as increased automation, the plant achieved an economic effect of 4.08 million soums. The cost of product production was reduced by 1.4%, and savings in raw materials and supplies amounted to 1.5 million soums. In 1973, technological processes in several key workshops, including methane conversion and urea production units, were fully automated¹.

At the Chirchik Electrochemical Plant (“Electrokhimkombinat”), the average level of automation in the main production workshops had reached 72.2% by that period. However, across the enterprise as a whole, this indicator still remained at 49.4%. During the period 1971–1975, a total of 184 measures related to the Scientific Organization of Labor (SOL) were

¹ Умурзакова Р. Развитие химической промышленности в Узбекистане в период 70-х – 80-х годов (история, опыт, проблемы). Дисс.Канд. ист.наук. –Т.: 1994. –С. 53

implemented. The overall economic effect of these measures amounted to approximately 260 thousand rubles, with an average return of 5–6 rubles in profit for every ruble invested. In subsequent years, efforts continued within the “Electrokhimprom” association to improve the efficiency of scientific researchers and to strengthen cooperation with research institutions. Significant work was carried out by five research sections of the Central Laboratory, as well as by the Scientific and Technical Information sector. Within the design and engineering department, a special sector for new technology was established, which was responsible for implementing advanced technologies in accordance with the plant’s development plans. Notably, between 1976 and 1980 alone, around 300 such measures were introduced².

Between 1971 and 1980, an entirely new direction in scientific research—namely, the use of low-temperature plasma for the synthesis of chemical products—developed rapidly. At the same time, research in such fields as radiation chemistry, the application of lasers, mathematical modeling of technological processes, and the development of new catalysts attracted considerable attention. Within a five-year period, more than 3,000 types of new chemical products were developed and introduced into practical use. As a result of improving the technical level of production, improving organizational and management forms, and refining methods of planning and economic incentives, the economic performance indicators of the industry showed significant improvement during the Ninth Five-Year Plan. In particular, more than 83% of the growth in output was achieved through increased labor productivity. Owing to the expansion of production scale and the more efficient use of material, energy, and labor resources, total profit in the sector increased by 2.4 times over the five-year period. It is especially noteworthy that the profit generated during this period exceeded the capital investments allocated to the sector by 1.3 times³. Between 1971 and 1980, owing to the major achievements of science and technology, the chemical industry emerged as one of the leading sectors of material production. Advances in the study of the mechanisms and dynamics of chemical reactions made it possible, within a relatively short period, to significantly expand the raw material base of the chemical industry. These developments created favorable conditions for the broader processing of natural gas and petroleum products, and laid the foundation for the production of polymer materials as well as a wide range of other chemical compounds⁴. At the same time, new academic departments were established. In accordance with the directive of the USSR Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, as well as Order No. 618 dated September 13, 1983, issued by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Uzbek SSR, measures were taken to streamline the organizational structure of departments within higher education institutions. As part of these reforms, at Tashkent State University, the Department of “Chemistry of Synthetic Polymers” was merged with the Department of “Chemistry of High-Molecular Compounds.” On this basis, a new unified department “Chemistry of Synthetic Polymers and High-Molecular Compounds” was established. Subsequently, increased attention was directed toward strengthening links between academic research in this field and industrial production⁵. These projects were

² Умурзакова Р. Развитие химической промышленности в Узбекистане в период 70-х – 80-х годов (история, опыт, проблемы). Дисс.Канд. ист.наук. –Т.: 1994. –С. 54.

³ Костандов А. Химическая промышленность на новом этапе развития. //Химическая промышленность, 1976. №2. С.(84).

⁴ Материалы XXV съезда КПСС, <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/XXV>

⁵ ЎзМА. Ф-Р2653. Р-1. Йж-5915. 1- варақ.

carried out at a high theoretical and experimental level and met all the established requirements for diploma work. The department also organized open lectures on selected topics, while the head of the department regularly monitored lecturers' teaching activities, including both lectures and practical classes, for quality assurance purposes. However, instruction in the general engineering discipline "Chemical Technology" was not delivered by specialists holding qualifications in chemical engineering. This was due to the absence of such personnel within the department⁶.

Uzbek chemists made a significant contribution to the development of polymer science. In recognition of this contribution, in 1979 a Department of Polymer Chemistry was established within the system of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. In 1981, it was reorganized into the Institute of Polymer Chemistry and Physics. The institute's staff conducted research in two principal areas: "Polymers for Medicine and Biology" and "Polymer Composite Materials." Such specialization is explained by the need to create physiologically active polymer-based materials for healthcare and agriculture. At the same time, the institute was tasked with developing specialized and structural materials to meet the demands of industry⁷.

Some research was conducted in cooperation with the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR Institute of Chemistry and the Tashkent Polytechnic Institute. Despite this collaboration, the industrial association still possessed a considerable amount of morally obsolete equipment, particularly metal-cutting machines, pumps, and compressors. Automated systems for technical production management were insufficiently implemented, and the strong scientific potential of the republic was not fully utilized in this field. At the Yangiyul Biochemical Plant, studies carried out jointly by the Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the Andijan Cotton Institute, and the Belarusian Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry demonstrated that lignin could be effectively used as an organic fertilizer. It was found to increase wheat yields and improve the agrophysical properties of soil. Field trials conducted on agricultural lands showed that applying 10–20 tons of lignin per hectare increased raw cotton yields by 2.0–2.2 centners per hectare. One of the notable centers where significant attention was paid to the introduction of scientific and technological progress was the city of Almalyk, particularly its chemical enterprises. Between 1971 and 1975, the Almalyk Chemical Plant achieved an economic effect of 4.3 million rubles through the introduction of new technologies. At the household chemicals plant, the implementation of new technological processes and the installation of additional equipment made it possible without major capital investments to increase the production of consumer goods by 500 thousand rubles in 1975. In 1978, the workforce of the Almalyk Chemical Plant, in cooperation with several research institutes, carried out extensive work to improve technological processes, eliminate bottlenecks and design flaws, install equipment, and reconstruct standard apparatuses for raw material processing. A number of innovations enabled fundamental changes in technological processes. These inventions were aimed at improving production efficiency, enhancing product quality,

⁶ ЎзМА. Ф-Р2653. Р-1. Йж-5915. 3- варақ

⁷ Рашидова С. Достижения института химии и физики полимеров ан УзССР за годы XI пятилетки и перспективы научных исследований на XII пятилетку. // Узбекский химический журнал. №5. 1985. С.29-33

improving working conditions for operational staff, and significantly reducing the consumption of raw materials and energy. Importantly, these innovations were applied not only at this plant but also at other existing and planned enterprises in the sector. As previously noted, it was here that, for the first time in global practice, a highly efficient technology for the direct extraction of phosphoric acid from low-grade ore was developed and implemented. As a result of comprehensive measures to improve product quality, in March 1978 the ammophos produced at the plant was awarded the State Quality Mark. At the same time, even at these advanced enterprises, numerous shortcomings remained in the implementation of plans for introducing new technologies⁸.

Chemical research was also carried out at a wide range of scientific and educational institutions. Among them were the Complex Institute of Natural Sciences under the Karakalpak Branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, as well as the Chirchik branch of the State Institute of the Nitrogen Industry and Basic Organic Synthesis Products. Research activities were likewise conducted within the “Uzkimyoplast” association and the Central Asian Design and Engineering Center, along with other similar institutions. In addition, extensive scientific work was undertaken at the chemistry departments and research laboratories of universities in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Nukus. Significant contributions were also made by the Tashkent Polytechnic Institute and its branches in Samarkand, Navoi, Almalyk, Angren, and Chirchik. Furthermore, research was actively pursued at the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, as well as at institutions specializing in pharmaceuticals and medicine, including the Andijan State Medical Institute. Other institutions involved included railway and automobile road institutes, the Fergana Polytechnic Institute, the Bukhara Institute of Technology of Light Industry, and pedagogical institutes in Tashkent, Bukhara, and Fergana, all of which conducted scientific research on a broad scale⁹. The development of chemical science was carried out in close cooperation between research institutes and higher education institutions, alongside organizations in related fields such as medicine, geology, biology, soil science, and agriculture. The primary objective of such interdisciplinary collaboration was to fulfill the key tasks set by the party and government—namely, to study the structure of substances and the synthesis of chemical compounds, to create new materials on this basis, to conduct in-depth investigations of natural resources, and to develop and improve integrated methods for their processing. The results of scientific research in the field of chemistry were published in central and republican scientific journals, including Uzbek Chemical Journal (“O‘zbekiston kimyo jurnali”), Chemistry of Natural Compounds (“Tabiiy birikmalar kimyosi”), and Proceedings of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (“O‘zFA xabarlari”), as well as in foreign publications. Notably, each issue of the journal Chemistry of Natural Compounds was translated into English and published accordingly. In addition, more than 150 printed sheets worth of scholarly output were published annually, including monographs, thematic collections, textbooks, teaching manuals, and popular science books and brochures¹⁰.

⁸ Умурзакова Р. Развитие химической промышленности в Узбекистане в период 70-х – 80-х годов (история, опыт, проблемы). Дисс.Канд. ист.наук. –Т.: 1994. –С. 54.

⁹ Арипов Э. Становление и развитие химических исследований в Узбекистане.// Узбекский химический журнал. №6. 1982 С.3-8.

¹⁰ Достижения химической науки в Узбекистане.//Узбекский химический журнал. №4.1967г. С.3-5.

By the late 1980s, negative public attitudes and critical publications regarding the activities of chemical enterprises also began to influence scientific research centers operating in this field. This can be observed from the following information. The pilot plant of the Scientific Research Institute of Cotton Cellulose Chemistry and Technology (NIICHTC) had a cotton cellulose workshop designed by the State Chemical Design Institute of the USSR (Goskhimproekt) and constructed in 1977. The main technological equipment of the workshop was developed according to individual engineering drawings, making it not only a unique experimental production facility in Uzbekistan, but also throughout the entire Soviet Union. The primary objective of this workshop was to master experimental production technologies for cotton cellulose and microcrystalline cellulose used for various purposes. It was planned that these products would replace imported goods and even become unique materials on the global market. Until 1989, cotton cellulose intended for products such as spectacle frames, sausage casings, electrolyte paper, color film and photographic films, filter cardboard, and lubricating substances for household air conditioners was developed and introduced into mass production. In addition, experimental batches of sorbents, fillers, carriers, and other substances based on microcrystalline and powdered cellulose were produced for use in medicine, chemistry, the food industry, and other sectors of the national economy. According to Order No. 517 of August 16, 1988, issued by the USSR Ministry of the Chemical Industry, the construction of the second stage of the Namangan Chemical Plant near the city of Chust was approved. The plant was designed to produce 40,000 tons of cotton cellulose and 90,000 tons of carboxymethyl cellulose annually. Experimental testing of the new plant's technology was to be carried out at the NIICHTC pilot production facility¹¹.

The analysis objectively demonstrates that the introduction of scientific and technological progress and innovative ideas in the chemical industry of Uzbekistan during the 1970–1980s were a complex and multifaceted process. During this period, certain achievements were attained: the level of automation in production processes increased, new technologies such as plasma synthesis, radiation chemistry, and laser-based methods were introduced into practice, the range of products expanded, and economic efficiency improved to a certain extent. In addition, the strengthening of cooperation between research institutes, higher education institutions, and industrial enterprises became an important factor in the development of the sector.

However, the presented evidence also shows that these achievements were not systemic or sustainable in nature. In many cases, scientific and technical initiatives remained largely formal, the introduction of new technologies was slow, and the modernization of outdated equipment progressed gradually. This hindered a significant increase in labor productivity and prevented production efficiency from reaching a higher level. In some enterprises, violations of technological discipline and issues related to product quality further highlighted existing shortcomings in the system.

At the same time, despite the available scientific potential, the mechanism for its full implementation in production was not sufficiently effective. This situation can be explained by centralized management structures, limited economic incentives, and organizational difficulties in introducing innovations. The examples mentioned in the text (Chirchik, Almalyk,

¹¹ ЎзМА. Ф-Р837. Р-14. ЙЖ-7580. 28-29-вақар

and Fergana enterprises) clearly illustrate this contradiction: on the one hand, significant scientific and technical progress, and on the other, persistent systemic problems.

Overall, although an innovative development process existed in the chemical industry of Uzbekistan during the 1970–1980s, it was not fully and effectively realized. The progress in the sector was constrained by a mismatch between scientific capabilities and practical implementation, as well as by organizational and technical barriers. In this regard, the experience of this period remains highly significant today, as it clearly demonstrates the importance of a systematic approach, modern management, and technological renewal in the implementation of innovation

